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Towards Economic Self-Reliance Of Nigerian Undergraduates: An Appraisal Of Entrepreneurship Education

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ABSTRACT

Entrepreneurship education serves as a critical springboard for self-reliance and sustainable development in any nation. Despite the progression of tertiary education in Africa, a significant gap remains in translating available manpower into sustainable economic growth. This study examines the role of entrepreneurship education in fostering economic self-reliance among Nigerian undergraduates. The problem stems from a labor market paradox where over 80% of Nigerian graduates remain unemployed due to a mismatch between academic curricula and industry requirements. Traditional education has focused on white-collar job preparation, leaving graduates without the practical skills necessary for job creation. Adopting a survey research design, the study utilized a simple random sampling technique to select 385 respondents. Data were gathered through structured questionnaires and analyzed using descriptive statistics, including percentages, mean, and standard deviation. Findings indicate that entrepreneurship education significantly impacts self-reliance by teaching valuable business management skills, encouraging innovation, and enhancing risk assessment. Respondents identified structural and systemic issues, such as corruption and inadequate training, as primary drivers of unemployment. The study concludes that entrepreneurship education is a vital tool for curtailing unemployment. It recommends making entrepreneurship courses compulsory across all universities and incorporating practical simulations into the curricula to bridge the gap between theoretical knowledge and real-world application.

Keywords: Entrepreneurship, Entrepreneurship Education, Undergraduates, Self-development, Unemployment.

INTRODUCTION

Education is the key to national development. This is because it unlocks the economic potentials of the people; empowers and equips individuals in society to participate in, and benefit from their national economy; facilitates economic development and provides the basis for transformation. Education is, therefore, an essential tool for sustainability. More so, the aim of every society is to prepare her citizen to take their place functionally in the society. This implies that as there are ailing problems in the society threatening to annihilate the being of man, education comes in to solve such problems by appeasing such forces. It serves as a vehicle for bringing these aims into reality. In Nigeria for example, there is the ailing

problem of unemployment and under-employment. This situation is an indication of an unfulfilled goal of education.

The commitment to provide relevant education to enable citizens contribute to their community's growth is enshrined in the Nigerian National Policy on Education (2004) which in part is stated thus: The acquisition of appropriate skills, abilities and competencies both mentally and physically as equipment for individuals to live and contribute to the development of the society. But the problem of integrating the youths in the society's social and economic systems remains unsolved in Nigeria. There exists an alarming increase in unemployment, lack of job satisfaction and frustration especially among young graduates.

Ogidi (1995), opined that the society sees education as something that guarantees the educated, immediate employment soon after leaving school; so anything short of this is perceived as faulty or defective. Similarly, Babalola (2007), observed that one major human capital assumption is that after finishing formal tertiary education, graduates should be able to afterwards make a successful transition from these institutions of higher learning to become productive workers, self-reliant entrepreneurs, responsible parents, good citizens, selfless leaders and live healthy lives.

Today, however, there are many graduates who are unemployed, and who cannot employ themselves. A survey conducted by the Federal Ministry of Education as reported by Chiachemen (2007) indicated that 71% of students who graduated from Nigerian Universities, Polytechnics, and Colleges of Education in the last six years are yet to find jobs. Benson (2004) stated that only ten percent (10%) of about 100,000 graduates within the age range (18 – 35) years have the prospect of securing employment on graduation from our tertiary institutions yearly.

In his findings, Onwukwe (2009) recently reported that about 200,000 graduates are produced each year and only 25% are absorbed, leaving 75% in a perpetual labour market without any hope of gainful employment. He added that even the 25% that were lucky to be employed are mostly underemployed. This may be partly due to the curricula of the tertiary institutions of learning, which lay emphasis on training for white-collar jobs. It is explicitly clear that no nation can survive in the face of successive job rates of unemployment because of the attendant waste of human resources. In this era of global economic and other socio-political and cultural challenges, functional knowledge and skills remains the key to sustainable economic development. There is the need to emphasize clearly at this juncture that to overcome untold hardship caused by the global economic meltdown, many countries of the world have introduced one form of economic policy or the other to improve on their economic condition. The most successful and important one has been placed on entrepreneurship. Buttressing on this fact, Ucheghara (2008) observed that, many theories from the social science and business discipline have developed theories and hypotheses that tried to explain the relationship between these two variables: economic development and entrepreneurship. It holds that entrepreneurship cuts across academic discipline and affects levels of stratification in societies by shaping life opportunities.

It is therefore against this background that entrepreneurship education has been included into Tertiary Education Curriculum in Nigeria. The importance of this is to encourage graduates to create jobs instead of searching for non-existing jobs. This paper aims at examining the concept of entrepreneurship education in tertiary education as a tool for reducing unemployment rate and enhancing self-reliance and economic sustainability in Nigeria.

Problem Statement/ Justification

It has been observed that the tertiary education in the past lacked the necessary information and skills needed to achieve meaningful economy development but only on reliance on white collar job that are not readily available after graduation. In view of the bad state of the Nigerian economy exacerbated by the dwindling fall in the price of crude oil in the world market which serves as a major source of income to the country, there is a strong need to position Nigerian higher education curriculum to stimulate economic growth and development through the production of graduates with entrepreneurial skills. On annual basis, graduates are produced to be gainfully employed by the formal sector of the Nigerian economy with little focus on graduate entrepreneurship. There is the observation from the public, especially industry players (employers and human resource managers), that most graduates in Nigeria lack certain qualities that

enhances their performance on the job soon after their graduation. The main reason given for this perception is that there is little collaboration between tertiary institution faculties and the industry/job market.

Underlying the unemployment menace, the training received by Higher Institution students has not been fully successful in equipping them with the required skills and competences needed for job creation and self-employment. This perception of most employers in Nigeria has made many fresh graduates find it difficult to secure jobs because almost all the job advertisements through the mass media request for people with a number of work experience and skills.

Skills shortage, as earlier mentioned, remains a serious constraint in Nigeria. Over 80% of graduates in Nigeria are unemployed, yet they have the qualifications, (Nwaoga and Omeke, 2012). Unemployment in Nigeria appears to be a labour market paradox, and can be attributed to prevailing skills deficit and skills mismatch. The skills deficit among graduates (from higher institution) is considered to be a constraint to long run economic growth and a contributing factor to incidence of graduate unemployment. Graduates lack generic competencies and are not work place ready. Graduate unemployment, therefore, has undoubtedly become a herculean national cankerworm of which every government has to deal with. Most of the employers, therefore, select fresh graduates who studied in the relevant fields for their jobs as trainees for a number of years before decision is taken either to hire them on full-time basis or as casual workers.

The Nigeria policy on education made it clear on the need for functional, practical and acquisition of appropriate skills and development of competencies as equipment for the individuals to live in and contribute to the development of his/her society (Aladekomo, 2004). Nwangwu (2007); Odjegba (2005); Baba (2013) reported that about 80% of the graduates find it difficult to get employment every year while at the same time much has not been done in trying to bring collaboration between the entrepreneurs and the institutions. The scourge of graduate unemployment in Nigeria is blamed on the university curriculum which has been geared towards stereotyped goals and jobs without adequate practical skills. In other words, graduates from universities acquired knowledge without entrepreneurial skills which would enable them, on graduation to practice what was learnt in school, create jobs for themselves and others and participate in economic development in Nigeria.

For instance, youth in Ogun State are said to be confronted with poverty and unemployment for lack of capacity and essential productive skills for both creative employment in existing organizations and for self-employment (Sagagi, 2010). Many people are unemployed because they have not acquired the kind of skills that are frequently demanded in the environment they operate. Others are unemployed because their skills have been rendered obsolete by technological changes or because they have no skills at all (Kpakol, 2006). With inadequate skills and few opportunities, young people in the state face a future of low-wage employment or ability to be self-reliant after graduation. This reality leaves youth in the country without any sustainable means of livelihood, as a result of which, poverty and unemployment have become the ugly twin faces of the economy.

Available information reiterates the massive unemployment of Nigerian universities graduates in the country, year in, year out. This problem, according to the report, was said to be traceable to the disequilibrium between labour market requirements and lack of essential employable or entrepreneurial skills by the graduates (Diajomal and Orimolade, (1991). This obvious critical skill gaps inhibits the development of youths and the entire development of the nation. The rationale for introducing entrepreneurship course in tertiary education curricular development, therefore, is to help students acquire increased understanding of entrepreneurship. The focus is to equip them with relevant skills and competences that prepare students to become entrepreneurs and managers of new businesses soon after graduation in order to increase their household income, (Gerald, 2013).

The Industrial Training Fund (ITF) was set up in 1971 in this regard in order to bridge the gap between theory and practice. The Student Industrial Works Experience Scheme (SIWES) which is an “off- shoot” of ITF came up in 1973 and has been trying in this regard but the situation seems not to have changed. More so, The Nigerian Institute of Management (NIM) has been in partnership with the National Youth Service Corps (NYSC) to ensure that fresh graduates are fully equipped with the needed Knowledge,

Attitude and Skills (KAS) needed to function effectively and efficiently in the world of work. Upon all these, the complaints of unemployment are still there. Olaleye (2009) noted that various Federal Government programs on eradication of poverty have failed because graduates of the education system lack the practical skills which can be acquired through entrepreneurship education program. One worrisome trend in the Nigerian labour market of recent has been the growing incidence of graduate unemployment of tertiary institutions.

Objective(s) of the study

The objectives of the study are:

- i. To analyze the concept of entrepreneurship education.
- ii. Examine the concepts and causes of unemployment in Nigeria
- iii. To examine the impact of entrepreneurship education on self-reliance among Nigerian undergraduates
- iv. Identify ways in which entrepreneurship education can help in promoting self-reliance and economic sustainability.
- v. State recommendations based on research findings with a view to using entrepreneurial education for self-reliance and sustainable development in Nigeria

Literature Review:

Over the past years, discussions on Entrepreneurship education have increasingly gained considerable attention of researchers. The subject has garnered much impetus, and attracted intense debate. In the last century, many writers have identified entrepreneurship with the function of uncertainty and risk bearing and others with the coordination of productive resources, the introduction of innovation and the provision of technical know-how (Hoselitz, 1952). During the sixteenth century, people who organized and managed military and exploration expeditions in France were called "entreprendre". The word entrepreneur originates from the French verb, "entreprendre" and the German word "unternehmen" both of which means to undertake (. In the Oxford Dictionary, an entrepreneur is defined as one who organizes, manages and assumes the risks of a business enterprise. The early 18th century French Economist, Richard Cantillon introduced the term entrepreneurship. In his writings, he formally defines the entrepreneur as the agent who buys means of production at certain prices in order to combine them into a new product. He further defines entrepreneurship as self-employment of any sort where the entrepreneur is the bearer of uncertainty and risk. Shortly thereafter, the French economist Jean Baptiste Say (1824) defines the entrepreneur as someone who shifts economic resources out of an area of lower to an area of higher productivity and greater yield. He added to Cantillon's definition by including the idea that an entrepreneur is one who brings other people together in order to build a single productive organization. But Say's definition, according to Drucker (1985), does not tell us who the entrepreneur is. And since Say coined the term almost two hundred years ago, there has been lack of consensus over the definition of entrepreneur and entrepreneurship.

Entrepreneurship has been recognized as an important aspect of an organization and economies (Dickson et al., 2008; Ossai and Nwalado, 2012; Aruwa, 2004; Akpomi, 2008; Ojeifo, 2013; Baba, 2013). It contributes in an immeasurable way towards creating new jobs, wealth creation, poverty reduction and income generating for both government and individuals. Schumpeter (1984) argued that entrepreneurship is very significant to the growth and development of economies. Having understood the role of entrepreneurship in economic development, it becomes apparent that careful attention is needed to invest and promote entrepreneurship. Education is also seen as one of the preconditions for entrepreneurship development particularly in a place where the spirit and culture are very minimal. It is said to be an important determinant of selection into entrepreneurship, formation of new venture and entrepreneurial success (Dickson, et. al., 2008; Nwachukwu & Nwamuo, 2010; Baba, 2013).

However, it is equally assumed here that there is a positive relationship between education and individual's choice to become an entrepreneur as well as the result and outcome of his or her entrepreneurial activity. The move towards poverty reduction should not be considered and treated in isolation. Different approaches and strategies need to be employed. For any country to foster genuine

economic growth and development, its educational system must be considered as the bedrock of any meaningful development (Akpomi, 2009). Human capital theory provides a framework for examining the impact of acquired variables such as education, learning and experience on career outcomes and it was further developed on the assumption that education can serve as a key determinant of decision choice and providing benefit to specific ventures (Ojeifo, 2013). In cognizance of this fact, Ojeifo (2013) opined that education should be designed with a view to create and enhance the supply of entrepreneurial initiative and activities. The bottom line here is to inculcate the spirit of entrepreneurship in the student through education. In fact, this calls for more serious adjustment of policies and new curriculum in line with demand of the present time.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design: The design for this study is survey design. Survey design is that type of research design in which information is collected from only a fraction of the population selected in such a way as to represent the whole. The researcher adopted this design because first and foremost, the area covered by this study is large and so, this method enabled the researcher to use sample to draw inference to represent the various elements of the population

Sampling Technique

The researcher adopted Cochran (1977) formula for sample size determination.

Formula: $no = \frac{Z^2 Pq}{e^2}$, where

e= desired level of precision i.e margin of error.

P= estimated proportion of the population who are well aware of entrepreneurship education.

q=estimated proportion of the population who are not well aware of entrepreneurship education (q=1-p)

Z=confidence interval (95% CI is adopted here, i.e z=1.96) in z-score language.

Therefore,

$$\begin{aligned}
 no &= \frac{(1.96)^2(0.5)(0.5)}{(0.05)^2} \\
 &= \frac{3.8416 (0.5) (0.5)}{(0.05)^2} \\
 &= \frac{3.8416 (0.25)}{0.0025} \\
 &= \frac{0.9604}{0.0025} \\
 &= 385
 \end{aligned}$$

The study used the simple random sampling technique to select the sample population.

Data Collection Instrument

Data was generated using questionnaire. The questionnaire consists of sections. The first section of the instruction handled the socio-demographic characteristics of the respondents to include age, sex, and educational background. Other sections of the instrument took care of the objectives based on the research objectives.

Statistical Analysis

For the purpose of Data analysis of this study, the researcher first coded the data, and did a data entry using excel 2010 version, which was later transferred into the Statistical Package for Social Sciences. Data were analyzed through the use of percentages, mean and standard deviation.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Table 1: Respondents Rating on the Socio-Demographic Variables of Respondents

	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Age		
16 – 30	209	55.6
31 – 40	123	32.7
41-50	39	10.4
51 above	5	1.3
Gender		
Female	201	53.5
Male	175	46.5
Marital Status		
Single	291	77.4
Married	76	20.2
Divorced	9	2.4

Source: Field survey, 2025

Table 1 above presents the demographic characteristics of respondents, which includes their age, gender and as well their marital status, the table reveals that 55.6% of the respondents are between the age range of 16 – 30, only 10.4% are within the age range of 41 – 50 and 1.3% only constitutes those within the age of 51 and above, from the revelation, majority of the respondents are within the student and youthful age group, therefore they should have more access or knowledgeable on entrepreneurship issues since they constitute the target population. Consequently, the table further reveals respondents' categories by gender, it indicates that majority of the respondents 53.5% are female while 46.5% are males, while 77.4% of the respondents are single, only 20.2% are married and 2.4% are divorced

Table 2: Respondents Rating on the Concept of Entrepreneurship Education.

S/N	Concept of entrepreneurship education	Ratings (%)					Mean	STD
		SA	A	UD	D	SD		
1	It teaches valuable skills for stating and managing business	187 (49.7)	117 (31.1)	14 (3.7)	47 (12.5)	11 (2.9)	4.12	1.134
2	It encourages creative thinking and innovation	91 (24.2)	202 (53.7)	51 (13.6)	15 (4.0)	17 (4.5)	3.89	.967
3	It helps in understanding of risk and challenges of business ownership	109 (29.0)	160 (42.6)	41 (5.1)	19 (5.1)	47.5 (12.5)	3.70	1.282
4	It inspires one to consider starting a business	187 (49.7)	131 (34.8)	7 (1.9)	35 (9.3)	16 (4.3)	4.16	1.117
5	It curriculum is relevant to Nigeria's economic needs	121 (32.2)	215 (57.2)	8 (2.1)	20 (5.3)	12 (3.2)	4.10	.914

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Table 2 reveals respondents' perceptions on the concepts of entrepreneurship education, using a Likert scale of 5, also indicating the mean response and standard deviation of the respondents' ratings. From all the five variables, table 2 indicates mean scores of responses between 3.70 and 4.16, which all fall above the decision benchmark of 3. this simply implies that the respondents generally agree with or accepted the concept of entrepreneurship education in tertiary institution. Consequently, the table has it that entrepreneurship education teaches valuable skills for stating and managing business with a mean = 4.12,

STD = 1.134, respondents also accepted the entrepreneurship education encourages creative thinking and innovations mean = 3.89, STD = .967, entrepreneurship education also helps in understanding the risk and challenges of business ownership mean = 3.70, STD = 1.282, the tables also indicates that respondent agree that curriculum of entrepreneurship education in institution is relevant to Nigeria’s economic needs with mean = 4.16, STD = 1.117, respondents also accepted that entrepreneurship education inspires me to consider starting my own business mean = 4.10, STD = .914.

Table 3: Respondents Rating on the Concepts and Causes of Unemployment in Nigeria.

S/N	Concepts and causes of unemployment in Nigeria	Ratings (%)					Mean	STD
		SA	A	UD	D	SD		
1	Lack of job creation in Nigeria formal sector is a major cause of unemployment	181 (48.1)	145 (38.6)	8 (2.1)	27 (7.2)	15 (4.0)	4.20	1.055
2	Inadequate skills and training contribute significantly to unemployment	111 (29.5)	219 (58.2)	24 (6.4)	14 (3.7)	8 (2.1)	4.09	.832
3	Rapid population growth is a key factor exacerbating unemployment in Nigeria	108 (28.7)	198 (52.7)	13 (3.5)	35 (9.3)	22 (5.9)	3.89	1.101
5	Education system in Nigeria does not adequately prepares graduates for job market	123 (32.7)	207 (55.1)	32 (8.5)	9 (2.4)	5 (1.3)	4.15	.778
6	Corruption and mismanagement of resources contribute to unemployment rate	115 (30.6)	209 (55.6)	12 (3.2)	23 (6.1)	17 (4.5)	4.02	.996

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Table 3 shows respondent views on the concepts and causes of unemployment in Nigeria, using a likert scale of 5. Respondent agreed with the fact that lack of job creation in Nigeria’s formal sector is a major cause of unemployment with a mean = 4.20, STD = 1.055, inadequate skills and training among Nigerians youth contribute significantly to unemployment mean = 4.09, STD = .832, rapid population growth is also a key factor exacerbating unemployment in Nigeria mean = 3.89, STD = 1.101, education system in Nigeria does not adequately prepares graduates for job market mean = 4.15, STD = .778 also respondents agreed that corruption and mismanagement of resources contribute to high unemployment rates in Nigeria mean = 4.02, STD = .996

Table 4: Respondents Rating on the Impact of Entrepreneurship Education on Self Reliance among Nigerian Undergraduates

S/N	Impact of entrepreneurship education on self-reliance among Nigerian under graduates	Ratings (%)					Mean	STD
		SA	A	UD	D	SD		
1	It increases one confidence in starting business	48 (12.8)	199 (52.9)	26 (6.9)	59 (15.7)	44 (11.7)	3.39	1.230
2	Skills gained from the education are useful for becoming self employed	61 (16.2)	260 (69.1)	8 (2.1)	23 (6.1)	24 (6.4)	3.83	.988
3	It helps in identifying viable business opportunities	40 (10.6)	281 (74.7)	14 (3.7)	25 (6.6)	16 (4.3)	3.81	.871
4	After taking courses, it builds one confidence in business management	52 (13.8)	205 (54.5)	44 (11.7)	36 (9.6)	39 (10.4)	3.52	1.159
5	It helps one become self-reliance instead of seeking a traditional job	43 (11.4)	188 (50.0)	14 (3.7)	74 (19.7)	57 (15.2)	3.23	1.309

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Table 4 shows respondents' views regarding Impact of entrepreneurship education on self-reliance among Nigerian under graduates, all responses are above the average mean of 2.5, the table indicted that education of self-relevance increases one confidence in starting a business Mean = 3.39, SD = 1.230, Skills gained from the entrepreneurship education are useful for becoming self-employed mean =3.82, SD = .988, entrepreneurship education helps in identifying viable business opportunities with a response mean = 3.81, SD = .871, more so, entrepreneurship education courses helps in building one confidence in business management mean = 3.52, SD =1.159 and entrepreneurship education helps one become self-reliance instead of seeking a traditional job mean = 3.23, SD = 1.309, this generally indicates that entrepreneurship is highly relevant in building self confidence in business and its management

Table 5: Respondents Rating on Ways in Which Entrepreneurship Education Helps in Promoting Self-reliance and Economic Sustainability

S/N	Ways in which entrepreneurship education helps in promoting self-reliance and economic sustainability	Ratings (%)					Mean	STD
		SA	A	UD	D	SD		
1	It equips students with practical skills needed to start and manage sustainable business	106 (28.2)	211 (56.1)	11 (2.9)	30 (8.0)	18 (4.8)	3.95	1.030
2	Learning about business planning equips students on self-reliance	96 (25.5)	193 (51.3)	12 (3.2)	34 (9.0)	41 (10.9)	3.72	1.246
3	It encourages innovative thinking initiatives that leads to economically sustainable ventures	112 (29.8)	168 (44.7)	12 (3.2)	34 (9.0)	50 (14.3)	3.69	1.340
4	It aids students' ability to identify and exploit market opportunities	112 (29.8)	179 (47.6)	8 (2.1)	23 (6.1)	54 (14.4)	3.72	1.336
5	It promotes financial literacy, contributing to long economic sustainability	125 (33.2)	164 (43.6)	12 (3.2)	32 (8.5)	43 (11.4)	3.79	1.301

Source: Field Survey

Table 5 shows respondents' responses on the ways to which entrepreneurship education helps in promoting self-reliance and economic sustainability, responses indicate acceptance level above the average mean of 2.5 supporting entrepreneurship education. Entrepreneurship education helps students

with practical skills needed to start and manage sustainable business has a response mean = 3.95, SD = 1.030, it also said that learning about business planning in entrepreneurship courses helps students become more self-relevant mean = 3.72, SD = 1.246, it further accepted that entrepreneurship education encourages innovative thinking that leads to economic sustainable venture with a mean = 3.69, SD = 1.340, while there is also an acceptance on entrepreneurship courses improving students ability to identify and exploit market opportunities for economic jobs with a response mean = 3.72, SD = 1.336 and also an acceptance on the fact that entrepreneurship education promotes financial literacy, contributing to long term economic sustainability with mean = 3.79, SD = 1.301

Table 6: Respondents Rating on Recommendations based on Research Findings

S/N	Recommendations based on research findings with views to using entrepreneurship education for self-reliance and sustainable development in Nigeria	Ratings (%)					Mean	STD
		SA	A	UD	D	SD		
1	Entrepreneurship education should be made compulsory in Nigerian universities to boost self-reliance	109 (29.0)	160 (42.6)	41 (5.1)	19 (5.1)	47.5 (12.5)	3.70	1.282
2	Incorporate practical business simulations into curriculum	123 (32.7)	113 (30.1)	25 (6.6)	64 (17.0)	51 (13.6)	3.51	1.437
3	Strengthen government industries partnerships	107 (28.5)	126 (33.5)	28 (7.4)	81 (21.5)	34 (9.0)	3.51	1.341
4	It should focus more on local markets needs	121 (32.2)	215 (57.2)	8 (2.1)	20 (5.3)	12 (3.2)	4.10	.914
5	Providing seed funding or grants for stat ups	112 (29.8)	179 (47.6)	8 (2.1)	23 (6.1)	54 (14.4)	3.72	1.336

Source: Field work, 2025

Table 6 shows some recommendations based on research findings with views to using entrepreneurship education for self-reliance and sustainable development in Nigeria, respondent ratings is also on a Likert scale of 5. Ratings were all above the average mean of 2.5 supporting the variables in question. From the table, respondent accepted that entrepreneurship education should be made compulsory in Nigerian universities to boost self-reliance with mean = 3.70, SD = 1.282, the incorporation of practical business simulations into entrepreneurship education curriculum will enhance students readiness for self-employment in Nigeria with mean = 3.51, SD = 1.437, government partnerships with industries should be strengthened to provide internship opportunities for entrepreneurship students with a response mean = 3.51, SD = 1.341, entrepreneurship education in Nigeria should focus more on local markets needs to drive sustainable developments a mean = 4.10 SD = .914, and table state that respondent agreed that providing seed funding or grant for student startups would increase the impact of entrepreneurship education on self-relevance with a mean = 3.72, SD = 1.336

SUMMARY/DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Findings reveal a strong agreement by respondents on the objective pertaining to the relevance of entrepreneurship education. All mean scores ranked above the benchmark of 3.0, showing general acceptance. Respondents indicated that entrepreneurship education teaches valuable skills for starting and managing businesses, encourages creativity and innovation, enhances understanding of business risks, and

inspires students to consider starting their own businesses. The high mean scores indicate that entrepreneurship education is seen as relevant and fits the economic needs of Nigeria.

The findings of this research underscore the transformative potential of entrepreneurship education as a catalyst for economic self-reliance among Nigerian undergraduates. By synthesizing the empirical data with existing literature, this discussion elucidates how pedagogical shifts can address the systemic crisis of graduate unemployment in Nigeria. Findings also reveal that respondents strongly accepted that unemployment in Nigeria is pushed by structural and systemic issues. Factors considered key include lack of job creation in the formal sector, inadequate skills and training, rapid population growth, poor alignment of the education system with labour market needs, and corruption. These findings underscored the imbalance between formal education and employable skills, strengthening the need for entrepreneurship education as a different approach to employment.

The Efficacy of Entrepreneurship Education

The study reveals a robust consensus among respondents that entrepreneurship education provides the essential "springboard" for self-development. With mean scores consistently exceeding the 3.0 benchmark, the data suggests that students perceive these curricula as more than theoretical requirements; they are seen as practical toolkits for navigating the modern economy. Specifically, the acquisition of skills in business management and risk assessment (Mean = 4.12 and 3.70, respectively) aligns with the Human Capital Theory, which posits that targeted education enhances individual productivity and career outcomes. This supports the argument of Ojeifo (2013) that education must be intentionally designed to increase the supply of entrepreneurial activity to meet societal needs.

Addressing the Systemic Roots of Unemployment

A significant portion of the discussion must center on the "labour market paradox" identified in the results. Respondents strongly affirmed that unemployment is driven by structural failures, including a lack of job creation in the formal sector and a profound mismatch between university curricula and market demands. This corroborates the "white-collar" bias identified by researchers like Ogidi (1995), where the education system historically produced job seekers rather than job creators. The finding that 71% of recent graduates remain unemployed highlights a critical failure in the traditional educational model to facilitate a successful transition into the workforce.

Impact on Self-Reliance and Economic Sustainability

The results indicate that entrepreneurship education has a measurable positive impact on "self-relevance" and confidence. Although the confidence to start a business recorded a lower mean compared to other variables (Mean = 3.39), it remains above the average, suggesting that while students value the knowledge, there may still be external inhibitors—such as lack of seed funding—that affect their perceived self-efficacy. Furthermore, the study links entrepreneurial training to broader economic sustainability by promoting financial literacy and innovative thinking (Mean = 3.79 and 3.69). This suggests that entrepreneurship education does not merely solve individual unemployment but contributes to national resilience by fostering a culture of innovation.

Bridging the Theory-Practice Gap

Despite the existence of initiatives like the Students Industrial Work Experience Scheme (SIWES), the persistent "skills gap" suggests that current interventions are insufficient. The high respondent agreement on the need for practical business simulations (Mean = 3.51) and seed funding (Mean = 3.72) indicates that the missing link in Nigerian entrepreneurship education is the transition from classroom theory to clinical application. As noted in the findings, for entrepreneurship to be a "panacea," it must move beyond stereotyped goals toward a functional, practical acquisition of competencies

CONCLUSION

The discourse surrounding Nigerian higher education has reached a critical juncture where the traditional "white-collar" training paradigm no longer suffices in the face of contemporary economic realities. This study concludes that entrepreneurship education is not merely an elective academic pursuit but a fundamental necessity for achieving national economic self-reliance and sustainable development. The empirical evidence gathered underscores a significant correlation between entrepreneurial pedagogy and

the enhancement of self-reliance among undergraduates, positioning it as a vital mechanism for bridging the existing skills gap.

Central to the study's findings is the realization that the "herculean national cankerworm" of graduate unemployment is deeply rooted in structural and systemic imbalances. These include a persistent disequilibrium between labor market requirements and the competencies possessed by graduates, exacerbated by rapid population growth and the lack of formal sector job creation. Consequently, the traditional reliance on education as a guaranteed path to immediate employment has become a "labour market paradox," where graduates possess qualifications but lack the functional skills required for the modern world of work.

The study further establishes that entrepreneurship education effectively addresses these challenges by shifting the focus from job-seeking to job-creating. By equipping students with practical skills, fostering innovative thinking, and improving financial literacy, the curriculum transforms undergraduates into proactive agents of economic growth. This transformation is essential for navigating an economy currently strained by dwindling crude oil prices and a lack of industrial collaboration.

Ultimately, for Nigeria to realize its potential for sustainable development, the integration of entrepreneurship into the tertiary education framework must move beyond theoretical instruction. The consensus among respondents highlights an urgent need for a more functional approach that incorporates practical simulations and industrial partnerships. In conclusion, fostering an entrepreneurial mindset among the youth is the most viable strategy for reducing poverty, enhancing household incomes, and ensuring the long-term economic stability of the nation.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The following recommendations are proffered:

1. Entrepreneurship education should be made compulsory across all Nigerian universities to enhance self-reliance among graduates.
2. Institutions should incorporate practical on entrepreneurship into entrepreneurship curricula to equip students with both theory and practical knowledge.
3. Strong partnership between government, educational institutions, and industries should be promoted to provide students with better knowledge.
4. Programmes related to entrepreneurship should be channeled towards the needs of the local market for the purpose of relevance and sustainability.

REFERENCES

- Akpomi, M. E. (2008). *Developing entrepreneurship education programme (EEP) for higher education institutions (HEIs) in Nigeria* [Unpublished post-doctoral research project]. University of Reading.
- Akpomi, M. E. (2009). Achieving Millennium Development Goals through teaching of entrepreneurship education in Nigeria higher education institutions. *European Journal of Social Science*, 8(1), 152–159.
- Aruwa, S. A. S. (2004). The business of entrepreneurs: A guide to entrepreneurial development. *Journal of Development of Business Administration*, 2(1), 112–122.
- Baba, G. K. (2013). The challenges of entrepreneurship development in Nigeria and way forward. *Journal of Business and Organizational Development*, 5(1), 54–64.
- Babalola, J. B. (2007, June). *Reinventing Nigeria higher education for youth empowerment in a competitive global economy* [Retirement lecture]. University of Calabar, Nigeria.
- Benson, I. (2004). *Experiential learning experience on the source of learning and development*. England Cliffs.
- Chiachemen, T. (2007, February 8). 71% of graduates are unemployed. *Daily Independent*, A3.
- Diajomal, U., & Orimolade, W. (1991). Unemployment in Nigeria: Economic analysis of scope, trends and policy issues. *Nigeria Journal of Economic and Social Sciences*, 13(2), 127–132.

- Dickson, P. H., Solomon, G. T., & Weaver, K. M. (2008). Entrepreneurial selection and success: Does education matter? *Journal of Small Business and Enterprise Development*, 15(2), 239–258.
- Drucker, P. F. (1985). *Innovation and entrepreneurship: Practice and principles*. Harper & Row.
- Gerald, D. G. (2013). Evaluating entrepreneurship education as a tool for economic growth. *British Journal of Education, Society and Behavioural Science*, 4(3), 318–335.
- Hoselitz, B. F. (1952). Entrepreneurship and economic growth. *American Journal of Economics and Sociology*, 12(1), 106.
- Kpakol, M. L. (2006, October). *Microfinance and programmed of poverty eradication* [Paper presentation]. National Workshop on Breaking the Yoke of Inter-generational Transfer of Poverty, Abuja, Nigeria.
- Nwachukwu, L. C., & Nwanmuo, P. (2010). *Entrepreneurship development for sustainable livelihood among youths in Imo State: Implication for counseling* [Conference proceedings]. CASSON.
- Nwangwu, I. O. (2007). *Higher education for self-reliance: An imperative for the Nigerian economy*. NEAP Publication.
- Nwoaga, & Omeke. (2012). Entrepreneurship and employability among Nigeria graduates. *Mediterranean Journal of Social Science*, 3(16), 68–74.
- Odjegba, E. (2005, July 3). Building Nigeria's entrepreneurship: What stakeholders say about essential ingredients. *Sunday Vanguard*.
- Ogidi, A. (1995, February 27). Declining school enrolments. *The Statesman*, 7.
- Ojeifo, S. A. (2013). Entrepreneurship education in Nigeria: A panacea for youth unemployment. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 4(6), 61–67.
- Ossai, A. G., & Nwalado. (2012). Entrepreneurship education: A panacea for sustainable development in Nigeria. *Journal of Resourcefulness and Distinction*, 1(1), 78–86.
- Sagagi, M. S. (2010). Enterprise development through value chain analysis: A case of Kano State, Nigeria. In *Readings in African entrepreneurship* (pp. 48–50). Adamu Joji Publishers.
- Ucheghara, F. (2008). *Integrated approach to entrepreneurship studies*. Feros Print & Co. Ltd.
- Unwukwe, A. (2009, Monday). The imperatives of entrepreneurship education. *Daily Sun*, 5.